

PROBLEMS IN REGULATING VEHICLES AND THEIR SOLUTIONS

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Abstract: The problems and their solutions in the regulation of vehicles are among many important problems. These problems may be related to infrastructure, traffic rules, ecology, and people's movement habits. defines the importance for In this article, several solutions and suggestions for the existing problems in the implementation of the above actions are shown.

Keywords: *movement, car, transport, safety, problem, solution, network, problem, solution, information, technology.*

Introduction Problems and solutions in the regulation of vehicles are among many important issues. These problems can be related to countries' infrastructure, traffic regulations, ecology, and people's movement habits. The transport system is an integral part of the modern world movement system. The main element of this system is people. It is impossible to plan the transport system without taking passengers into account, just as it is impossible to imagine transport without people in the current conditions. It must be admitted that today the condition of the transport system not only in Samarkand city, but also in almost all regions of our republic is not satisfactory. Especially since the number of private cars and the population is increasing, the issue of transportation has become one of the most painful problems of the city of Samarkand. In the last 10 years, the number of cars in the city has more than doubled, on top of that, the public transport network was established in the 2000s, but it has not been completely revised until now, as a result, serious problems have accumulated in the city's public transport

system. is complicating the existing situation more and more. The following problems and their solutions can be comprehensively indicated [1-2]

According to data, cars consume more than 25 tons of fuel in one hour of traffic jam, and also emit a lot of harmful gases into the atmosphere, fuel is wasted, and most importantly, people lose their precious time. This requires further expansion of the roads of our city, construction of new roads and bridges.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

According to the data of the State Statistics Committee, as of January 1, 2022, the total number of private cars in our republic is 3 million 51 thousand 734.

The total number of motor vehicles owned by the population in the last 5 years.

- 2016 y. 1 974 182 ta;
- 2017 y. 2 057 331 ta;
- 2018 y. 2 133 507 ta;
- 2019 y. 2 272 185 ta;
- B 2020 y. 2 410 421 ta;
- 2021 y. 2 767 126 ta;

From these data, it can be seen that the number of vehicles is increasing significantly from year to year, and this in turn means that city dwellers suffer from traffic jams, poor quality public transport services, wasted time not only during commuting to and from work , but also at other times of the day. facing a number of problems such as

The inability of our intersections to respond to the flow of cars coming from different directions is also a serious inconvenience. Therefore, it is possible to prevent the intersection of highways on different routes by building underground roads or overpasses (a structure where roads for vehicles and pedestrians are passed at a certain height from the ground; bridge) at intersections.[3-5]

Private vehicles make up the main "share" of road traffic. One of the ways to prevent this is to increase the number of public transport and increase the percentage of public transport use.

In this process, it is necessary to take into account some factors such as the mentality and individuality of the population. For example, in a study of social habits, among the reasons for preferring public transport, the following parameters are said to come to the fore:

- price on the bus route;
- Proximity between the exit and drop-off points on the minibus route;
- speed and price in railway transport;
- speed and comfort in a taxi.
- In order to reduce the problems associated with public transport, it is important to implement the following:
 - increasing the number of public transport;
 - to increase the use of public transport during the busiest hours - during the commute to and from work;
 - extension of railway transport, in particular tram lines, to areas where public transport is insufficient;
 - re-planning of the city's internal bus routes, their travel intervals and distances according to the density level and needs of the population.

Organization of various centers within the city.

In cities with a single center, a large part of the population flows towards the center for a number of reasons, such as work, housing, public services, and transportation. In such a situation, the city center will be under severe pressure of people and vehicles. In order to reduce this pressure when the master plan of the city is being drawn up, it is necessary to create small centers that have all kinds of amenities in other areas, including state institutions, new buildings, higher education institutions and the like, thereby reducing the traffic in the city center and making the city a multi-centered one. can be converted into an area.[6-7]

Arrangement of roads in accordance with new housing.

Especially in recent years, the appearance of our city is changing radically as a result of the construction of multi-storey luxury houses with their own social facilities. In short, the development of public transport is a comprehensive issue that requires both a scientific and a practical approach.[8]

Creation of bicycle lanes and pedestrian facilities.

One of the most environmentally friendly types of transport is undoubtedly bicycles. But although in most foreign countries the practice of using bicycles and the creation of the necessary conditions for this began many years ago, in our country work on this began to be focused mainly in recent years. But this attention is not yet enough. Because it is difficult to meet such roads and squares

in most of the remaining regions of the capital, when Parks, some anhor and Canal Shores, some areas with corridors (some are simply not difficult to notice that they are taken for granted)are excluded.

It is worth noting that the expansion of the bike lane network throughout the city is also important in terms of the point of reducing traffic load. One system that should be introduced in order to ensure pedestrian safety is the pedestrian button system. This system is usually set up at intersections, with the aim of ensuring safe passage of pedestrians at permanent or at certain times of the day at non-intersecting entrances and exits of pedestrian crossings. Of course, the alarm system of intersections should be introduced according to the ratio of traffic density and its use.[9]

Increasing alternative routes

One of the main reasons for traffic jams is the lack of alternative roads. Cars should be able to arrive at the busiest points of the city through alternative routes and leave the area again on alternative routes. This is one of the solutions recommended by transportation engineering.

In addition, in times of disaster and war, the area of emergency situations where the city's population accumulates, and alternative roads leading to these areas, must be taken into account in the

general plan of the city.

Road widening and construction of trestles

Narrow and later narrowed roads, as well as intersections, are places where traffic jams are observed at the highest level. Especially after a certain point, the number of rows decreases, and traffic jams on narrowing roads are inevitable. Therefore, when drawing up road plans, it is better to try to avoid such narrow-mouthed roads as much as possible.

Another problem is that our main roads are not wide enough to handle the traffic density. One of the important precautions that should be taken on such narrow roads is the prevention and control of vehicles being left on the side of the road.

The inability of our intersections to respond to the flow of cars coming from different directions is also a serious inconvenience. Therefore, it is necessary to prevent the crossing of highways on different routes by building underground roads or overpasses at intersections. can be obtained.[10]

Increasing the number of parking spaces. Promote Park and Ride system. In big cities, especially in the capital, the increase in the number of vehicles is not parallel to the increase in parking spaces. Naturally, the lack of "parking lots" leads to an increase in cases of illegal parking on the roads. This situation, in turn, causes problems related to transport to become more complicated.

In most countries, for example, in England, as well as in Istanbul, Turkey, special attention is paid to finding a solution to this problem through the Park and Ride system and thereby directing people to public transport. According to the Park and Ride system, people driving to the city center leave their cars in free or discounted parking at public transport stations and continue the rest of the way by public transport. Of course, traffic congestion can be reduced by using this system.

In addition, the construction of multi-story or underground parking lots, as well as making the construction of parking lots mandatory in new residential areas, will be the basis for the creation of infrastructure that will meet the current needs, as well as the future increase in the number of motor vehicles.

Development of public transport. This is one of our most painful points. In this regard, it is not difficult to see how sad the general scene in the capital is from the videos and photos that have been circulating on social networks recently.

Private vehicles make up the main "share" of road traffic. One of the ways to prevent this is to increase the number of public transport and increase the percentage of public transport use.

In this process, it is necessary to take into account some factors such as the mentality and individuality of the population. For example, in one study of social habits, among the reasons for preferring public transport, the following parameters are said to come to the fore:

- price on the bus route;
- proximity between the exit and the drop point in the direction of the minibus;
- speed and price in rail transport;
- speed and comfort in a taxi.
- In reducing the problems associated with public transport, the implementation of the following plays an important role:
- increase the number of public transport;
- the busiest hours of public transport - increase in the time of going to work and returning from work;
- rail transport, in particular, the extension of metro lines to areas where public transport is insufficient;

- rescheduling the inner city bus routes, their commute intervals and distances according to population density level and need.

1.Environmental issues:

- Solution: high emission of fuel plants, vehicles, and land hazardous substances made of.
- Refinement of kerosene, diesel and battery sauerkraut certificates.
- The development of electric vehicles and the upgrade of the initial movement.

2.Fertile transport time:

Solution: minimize time to move and pass on the road.

Improvement of road infrastructure and integration of transport networks.

Development of expanded transport systems (metro, tram, passenger).

3.Parking and parking problems of cars on the road:

Solution: car parking spaces and traffic regulation.

Solving related parking problems of Housing and workplaces.

In order for these problems to be addressed comprehensively, States, enterprise and community organizations must also have a strong access to the technology and innovation department.

Information technology (it) and Smart transportation: IT and communication technologies provide an opportunity to monitor and control the movement of vehicles on the road. It works in the optimization of technologies, automatic surgical systems, road States, and road parking times. Smart transportation systems play an important role in the expansion of cities, in particular, the consequences of average time and traffic.

Automotive biology and technology: changing automotive technology is bringing new high experience levels with high efficiency. Such innovations include hybrid and electric cars, self-taught car systems, and automatic self-development systems.

Automotive Energy and deadlines: their opposition to the installation of kerosene, diesel and gas transport has guides and innovations regarding the proper study of right-grip and electric-powered vehicles. Such technologies have attracted investments of high hundreds of miles of milliar dollars and have increased the fight against energy consumption and environmental changes.

Car deposits and orders: problems in the regulation of transport, the average supply of parking and security and car deposits, for example, require changes. It requires solving the problem through the comfort of cars, security systems, and the changing and handwriting comfort of its employees.

Innovations in the Transport fields: innovations in the field of vehicle regulation are developing comprehensively. For example, automatic transportation, migration systems, communication through vehicles, and automated parking systems are important. One system that should be introduced in order to ensure pedestrian safety is the pedestrian button system. This system is usually set up at intersections, with the aim of providing safe passage of pedestrians at permanent or certain times of the day at intersections and exits of pedestrian spaces without intersections. Of course, the alarm system of intersections should be introduced according to the ratio of traffic density and its use.

Increase in CAR Housing. Park and Ride system application.

The increase in the number of motor vehicles in large cities, in particular in the city of Samarkand, is

not parallel with the increase in parking spaces. It is necessary that there are cases of illegal parking in ways of insufficient "stoyanka". Leads to reproduction. This situation, in turn, causes problems with transportation to become more complicated. In most countries, such as England, as well as Istanbul, Turkey, special attention is paid to finding a solution to this problem through the Park and Ride system and thereby diverting people to public transport. According to the Park and Ride system, people who drive to the city center leave their cars in free or discounted parking lots located at public transportation stations and continue the rest of the route on public transportation. Of course, it is possible to reduce traffic in roads by using this system.

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